

“How Long to Wait?” Patience as the Key at Crisis – Corona and the Story of Job

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Faced with the miserable crisis of Corona virus, we are rendered uncertain, fearful, desperate and suspicious. Once again crops up the age-old question: Why is there evil in the world, if God is omniscient, omnipotent und omnibenevolent? We ask the question: Why should humanity suffer under such a contagious disease? We have never found, nor would we be able to find a conclusive answer to this question. A crisis like this Corona pandemic once again exposes our ‘ignorance’ in spite of all the claimed and acclaimed enlightenment and advancement. We don’t and we cannot lessen the esteem and value of the knowledge about reality acquired through science. And yet, everything proves insufficient at a moment like this. We cannot do much about this crisis except watching, waiting, praying and supporting one another.

Our predicament reminds us of and relates us to the biblical character Job. Just like Job, we are all undergoing a crisis having no idea about the why of it. Now let us spend a few minutes reflecting on the different stages Job went through at the time of his suffering and see if it is going to help us to cope with our situation. The spread of the Corona-Pandemic happens in stages as happened Job’s misery. These two can be compared indirectly:

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Job’s Misery	Corona Pandemic
Remote scene in heaven in which God empowers Satan to harm Job’s possessions (Job 1:6-12)	December 2019: The news of a new Virus breakout far away from us in Wuhan in China
Job loses his riches and his children (Job 1:13-22): Job loses first his oxen and servants (v 15), second his sheep and servants (v 16), third his camels and servants (v 17) and fourth his sons and daughters (vv 18-19). Job’s Reaction (vv 20-22): Job is upset, yet he accepts the losses as ‘will of God’ and does not charge against God. Remains faithful to God in whom he believes.	February 2020: The Corona Virus has reached Iran, Italy and Spain, infecting thousands of them and killing people in large numbers, then it reached other European countries. In USA it is infecting hundreds of thousands of the people and kills thousands of them. General Reaction: It is terrible! God save them all! Let us not worry too much about it. We are not yet affected. The virus will get killed in the Indian heat and will not affect us so badly!
Job loses his health (Job 2:6-9): With full of sores on his body, scratching himself with a potsherd and cursed by his wife. Job’s Response (Job 2:10). One should be ready to receive from God the bad as well.	March 22: A 14-hour curfew in India. Now it is next doors. Fear and uncertainty strengthened. Our Response: We trust in God and He will help us to overcome this pandemic!

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The story continues. Job is visited by his three friends and initially they do the right thing by sitting with Job on the ground for seven days and seven nights without uttering a word (Job 2:13). After these seven days and seven nights Job breaks the silence and begins to curse his birth. This is the first moment of his impatience. As adding fuel to the fire, each of Job’s three friends deliver three theological speeches each (Job 4:1-27:23) seeking a causative justification to Job’s suffering. This unsettles Job further and he becomes rebellious accusing God of handling him unjustly and ends up demanding a just trial by God: “let me be weighed in a just balance, and let God know my integrity!” (31:6). Job has actually become absolutely impatient. He wants to know why an innocent person like him should suffer. Even the four speeches of Elihu (Job 32:1-37:24)

who tries to convince Job that Job ‘speaks without knowledge and his words are without insight’ (Job 34:35) fail to convince him of God’s just ways (Job 34:10-15). Finally, only a direct speech by God himself (Job 38:1-41:26) reveals Job’s ignorance to him, after which he is able to surrender himself to God admitting that he uttered what he did not understand, things too wonderful for him, which he did not know (Job 42:3).

Job started off well. However, as the redemption from his misery got delayed he became more and more impatient and went to the extent of questioning the very foundations of his life, his faith and his relationships. Now we too experience a delay. There is not yet an anti-biotic nor any vaccination which can be used against or protect us from this virus. We too are tempted to become impatient and question the foundations on which we have built our life and relationships. Yet, delays are not to be understood as denials.

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On Saturday, 14th March 2020, at the spread of this virus in many of the western countries, said Zimbabwe’s defence minister Oppah Muchinguri, speaking at a rally in the northern town of Chinhoyi in Zimbabwe, “Coronavirus is the work of God punishing countries who imposed sanctions on us.”¹ Such negative approaches and attitudes express the sheer helplessness and ill-feelings and would only worsen the menace. At this moment of the crisis, no fault-

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findings, no false consolations, no grumbling, no justifications neither theological nor philosophical, are going to bring us further.

Pope Francis compares the Corona crisis to the great windstorm of Mark 4:37 and rightly asserts that this storm “exposes our vulnerability and uncovers those false and superfluous certainties” and “In this storm, the façade of those stereotypes with which we camouflaged our egos, always worrying about our image, has fallen away, uncovering once more that (blessed) common belonging, of which we cannot be deprived: our belonging as brothers and sisters.”²

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With the Corona-Pandemic we have all been thrown into a similar situation like that of Job. The only right thing that happened at Job’s crisis was the accompaniment of his three friends during the first seven days and seven nights. The Corona crisis also demands a similar type of solidarity and reveals that we all belong together. This crisis has rendered most of our social, economic, intellectual and religious statuses and stratifications meaningless. The meaningful thing that we could now do is first to watch and wait patiently and then make efforts to reach out a helping hand to those who are affected.

So let us be patient, patient till the end.

Let us express our solidarity by maintaining sufficient distance.

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Let us restrict our movements to our own families and communities.

And let us persevere in our prayers for ourselves and for all those who are affected, especially, those whose immediate future is endangered.

¹ <https://gulfnews.com/world/africa/zimbabwe-minister-coronavirus-gods-punishment-for-west-1.70401945> published on 15 March 2020 and accessed on 30.03.2020.

² Pope Francis, Extraordinary Moment of Prayer, Sagrato of St Peter's Basilica, Vatican, 27 March 2020.